

Supplementary Table 2

Pairwise root support tests for two datasets: **a) Opisthokonta**; and **b) Proteobacteria**.

Values are FDR adjusted p-values of the two-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test and the sample size.

Arrows point to the significantly better supported candidate root partition (FDR 0.05).

a)

Opisthokonta - 31 species
All gene families - 13036 trees
7 Candidate partitions

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1		← 1.5×10 ⁻¹²² 2064	← 1.3×10 ⁻¹⁹⁵ 2103	← 2.4×10 ⁻²¹⁰ 2554	← 1.0×10 ⁻³⁰⁹ 2369	← < 10 ⁻³²³ 2436	← < 10 ⁻³²³ 2593
2	↑ 1.5×10 ⁻¹²² 2064		← 8.9×10 ⁻⁴⁸ 1754	← 8.0×10 ⁻⁹¹ 2629	← 3.9×10 ⁻²⁰⁸ 1943	← 4.0×10 ⁻²⁷⁵ 1977	← 3.5×10 ⁻²⁶³ 2055
3	↑ 1.3×10 ⁻¹⁹⁵ 2103	↑ 8.9×10 ⁻⁴⁸ 1754		↑ 1.7×10 ⁻²⁹ 2057	← 8.1×10 ⁻²⁶³ 3217	← < 10 ⁻³²³ 3323	← 1.8×10 ⁻³⁰⁶ 3068
4	↑ 2.4×10 ⁻²¹⁰ 2554	↑ 8.0×10 ⁻⁹¹ 2629	← 1.7×10 ⁻²⁹ 2057		← 3.3×10 ⁻¹⁸⁴ 2309	← 7.2×10 ⁻²⁷⁸ 2374	← 6.1×10 ⁻²⁶⁶ 2521
5	↑ 1.0×10 ⁻³⁰⁹ 2369	↑ 3.9×10 ⁻²⁰⁸ 1943	↑ 8.1×10 ⁻²⁶³ 3217	↑ 3.3×10 ⁻¹⁸⁴ 2309		← 2.4×10 ⁻⁹³ 4512	← 1.9×10 ⁻¹³⁶ 3995
6	↑ < 10 ⁻³²³ 2436	↑ 4.0×10 ⁻²⁷⁵ 1977	↑ < 10 ⁻³²³ 3323	↑ 7.2×10 ⁻²⁷⁸ 2374	↑ 2.4×10 ⁻⁹³ 4512		← 4.2×10 ⁻¹⁸ 4120
7	↑ < 10 ⁻³²³ 2593	↑ 3.5×10 ⁻²⁶³ 2055	↑ 1.8×10 ⁻³⁰⁶ 3068	↑ 6.1×10 ⁻²⁶⁶ 2521	↑ 1.9×10 ⁻¹³⁶ 3995	↑ 4.2×10 ⁻¹⁸ 4120	

Opisthokonta - 31 species
CSC gene families - 170 trees
7 Candidate partitions

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1		← 3.7×10 ⁻¹⁷ 170	← 8.6×10 ⁻²⁶ 170	← 7.3×10 ⁻²⁴ 170	← 6.9×10 ⁻²⁸ 170	← 2.7×10 ⁻²⁸ 170	← 1.1×10 ⁻²⁷ 170
2	↑ 3.7×10 ⁻¹⁷ 170		← 8.0×10 ⁻¹⁰ 170	← 2.3×10 ⁻¹⁰ 170	← 1.9×10 ⁻²⁵ 170	← 2.9×10 ⁻²⁸ 170	← 2.7×10 ⁻²⁸ 170
3	↑ 8.6×10 ⁻²⁶ 170	↑ 8.0×10 ⁻¹⁰ 170		↑ 9.0×10 ⁻⁹ 170	← 1.4×10 ⁻²³ 170	← 3.0×10 ⁻²⁵ 170	← 2.7×10 ⁻²⁸ 170
4	↑ 7.3×10 ⁻²⁴ 170	↑ 2.3×10 ⁻¹⁰ 170	← 9.0×10 ⁻⁹ 170		← 8.6×10 ⁻²⁶ 170	← 6.2×10 ⁻²⁸ 170	← 2.9×10 ⁻²⁸ 170
5	↑ 6.9×10 ⁻²⁸ 170	↑ 1.9×10 ⁻²⁵ 170	↑ 1.4×10 ⁻²³ 170	↑ 8.6×10 ⁻²⁶ 170		← 3.8×10 ⁻¹⁷ 170	← 1.3×10 ⁻²⁴ 170
6	↑ 2.7×10 ⁻²⁸ 170	↑ 2.9×10 ⁻²⁸ 170	↑ 3.0×10 ⁻²⁵ 170	↑ 6.2×10 ⁻²⁸ 170	↑ 3.8×10 ⁻¹⁷ 170		← 0.00012 170
7	↑ 1.1×10 ⁻²⁷ 170	↑ 2.7×10 ⁻²⁸ 170	↑ 2.7×10 ⁻²⁸ 170	↑ 2.9×10 ⁻²⁸ 170	↑ 1.3×10 ⁻²⁴ 170	↑ 0.00012 170	

Opisthokonta - 31 species
CMC gene families - 612 trees
7 Candidate partitions

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1		← 7.4×10 ⁻³⁶ 612	← 1.9×10 ⁻⁵⁰ 612	← 2.6×10 ⁻⁶⁰ 612	← 5.7×10 ⁻⁷⁸ 612	← 2.3×10 ⁻⁸⁷ 612	← 1.9×10 ⁻⁸⁷ 612
2	↑ 7.4×10 ⁻³⁶ 612		← 1.6×10 ⁻¹⁰ 612	← 1.2×10 ⁻²⁶ 612	← 3.7×10 ⁻⁶³ 612	← 8.8×10 ⁻⁸⁸ 612	← 3.1×10 ⁻⁹⁰ 612
3	↑ 1.9×10 ⁻⁵⁰ 612	↑ 1.6×10 ⁻¹⁰ 612		≈ 0.11 612	← 6.9×10 ⁻⁶¹ 612	← 6.8×10 ⁻⁷⁸ 612	← 4.5×10 ⁻⁸⁸ 612
4	↑ 2.6×10 ⁻⁶⁰ 612	↑ 1.2×10 ⁻²⁶ 612	≈ 0.11 612		← 2.2×10 ⁻³⁷ 612	← 6.1×10 ⁻⁷⁰ 612	← 2.2×10 ⁻⁷⁶ 612
5	↑ 5.7×10 ⁻⁷⁸ 612	↑ 3.7×10 ⁻⁶³ 612	↑ 6.9×10 ⁻⁶¹ 612	↑ 2.2×10 ⁻³⁷ 612		← 4.1×10 ⁻⁴⁵ 612	← 1.5×10 ⁻⁵⁹ 612
6	↑ 2.3×10 ⁻⁸⁷ 612	↑ 8.8×10 ⁻⁸⁸ 612	↑ 6.8×10 ⁻⁷⁸ 612	↑ 6.1×10 ⁻⁷⁰ 612	↑ 4.1×10 ⁻⁴⁵ 612		← 2.0×10 ⁻⁸ 612
7	↑ 1.9×10 ⁻⁸⁷ 612	↑ 3.1×10 ⁻⁹⁰ 612	↑ 4.5×10 ⁻⁸⁸ 612	↑ 2.2×10 ⁻⁷⁶ 612	↑ 1.5×10 ⁻⁵⁹ 612	↑ 2.0×10 ⁻⁸ 612	

Opisthokonta - 31 species
PSC gene families - 7773 trees
7 Candidate partitions

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1		← 4.9×10 ⁻³⁵ 410	← 3.4×10 ⁻⁵⁰ 384	← 1.2×10 ⁻⁴⁷ 571	← 1.1×10 ⁻⁷³ 506	← 1.3×10 ⁻⁷⁸ 521	← 3.3×10 ⁻⁶⁵ 588
2	↑ 4.9×10 ⁻³⁵ 410		← 3.2×10 ⁻¹³ 291	← 4.6×10 ⁻²⁰ 806	← 1.3×10 ⁻⁴⁵ 374	← 8.3×10 ⁻⁵⁵ 380	← 5.2×10 ⁻⁴³ 406
3	↑ 3.4×10 ⁻⁵⁰ 384	↑ 3.2×10 ⁻¹³ 291		↑ 9.1×10 ⁻¹⁵ 365	← 1.1×10 ⁻⁷¹ 790	← 3.4×10 ⁻⁷⁵ 821	← 1.0×10 ⁻⁶³ 707
4	↑ 1.2×10 ⁻⁴⁷ 571	↑ 4.6×10 ⁻²⁰ 806	← 9.1×10 ⁻¹⁵ 365		← 5.8×10 ⁻⁵⁰ 479	← 2.7×10 ⁻⁶⁴ 493	← 2.7×10 ⁻⁵² 553
5	↑ 1.1×10 ⁻⁷³ 506	↑ 1.3×10 ⁻⁴⁵ 374	↑ 1.1×10 ⁻⁷¹ 790	↑ 5.8×10 ⁻⁵⁰ 479		← 4.2×10 ⁻¹⁰ 1444	← 1.8×10 ⁻²⁷ 1170
6	↑ 1.3×10 ⁻⁷⁸ 521	↑ 8.3×10 ⁻⁵⁵ 380	↑ 3.4×10 ⁻⁷⁵ 821	↑ 2.7×10 ⁻⁶⁴ 493	↑ 4.2×10 ⁻¹⁰ 1444		← 9.1×10 ⁻¹⁵ 1211
7	↑ 3.3×10 ⁻⁶⁵ 588	↑ 5.2×10 ⁻⁴³ 406	↑ 1.0×10 ⁻⁶³ 707	↑ 2.7×10 ⁻⁵² 553	↑ 1.8×10 ⁻²⁷ 1170	↑ 9.1×10 ⁻¹⁵ 1211	

Opisthokonta - 31 species

PMC gene families - 4481 trees

7 Candidate partitions

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1		← 2.4×10 ⁻⁴² 872	← 6.9×10 ⁻⁷⁸ 937	← 5.5×10 ⁻⁸⁵ 1201	← 5.1×10 ⁻¹³⁵ 1081	← 3.9×10 ⁻¹⁵⁴ 1133	← 5.3×10 ⁻¹⁴⁷ 1223
2	↑ 2.4×10 ⁻⁴² 872		← 4.0×10 ⁻²¹ 681	← 1.9×10 ⁻³⁹ 1041	← 2.6×10 ⁻⁷⁹ 787	← 4.0×10 ⁻¹⁰⁷ 815	← 4.3×10 ⁻⁹⁸ 867
3	↑ 6.9×10 ⁻⁷⁸ 937	↑ 4.0×10 ⁻²¹ 681		↑ 9.1×10 ⁻¹⁷ 910	← 2.1×10 ⁻¹¹⁰ 1645	← 2.0×10 ⁻¹⁴⁷ 1720	← 6.9×10 ⁻¹²² 1579
4	↑ 5.5×10 ⁻⁸⁵ 1201	↑ 1.9×10 ⁻³⁹ 1041	← 9.1×10 ⁻¹⁷ 910		← 1.2×10 ⁻⁷⁹ 1048	← 8.7×10 ⁻¹¹⁹ 1099	← 2.1×10 ⁻¹¹⁰ 1186
5	↑ 5.1×10 ⁻¹³⁵ 1081	↑ 2.6×10 ⁻⁷⁹ 787	↑ 2.1×10 ⁻¹¹⁰ 1645	↑ 1.2×10 ⁻⁷⁹ 1048		← 3.4×10 ⁻⁴⁰ 2286	← 1.4×10 ⁻⁴⁷ 2043
6	↑ 3.9×10 ⁻¹⁵⁴ 1133	↑ 4.0×10 ⁻¹⁰⁷ 815	↑ 2.0×10 ⁻¹⁴⁷ 1720	↑ 8.7×10 ⁻¹¹⁹ 1099	↑ 3.4×10 ⁻⁴⁰ 2286		← 0.0015 2127
7	↑ 5.3×10 ⁻¹⁴⁷ 1223	↑ 4.3×10 ⁻⁹⁸ 867	↑ 6.9×10 ⁻¹²² 1579	↑ 2.1×10 ⁻¹¹⁰ 1186	↑ 1.4×10 ⁻⁴⁷ 2043	↑ 0.0015 2127	

